

Workplace Equity and Job Satisfaction among Academic Staff in Western Uganda Universities

Annah Tugaineyo*

Assistant Lecturer, Valley University of Science and Technology.

*Corresponding Author

Annah Tugaineyo

Assistant Lecturer, Valley University of Science and Technology.

Article History

Received: 23.07.2024

Accepted: 06.08.2024

Published: 14.08.2024

Abstract: Job satisfaction among academic staff in western Ugandan universities positively correlates with the level of workplace equity, employees' participation in staff committees, and welfare. Every workplace is expected to be conducive to all employees. Employees in a secure and good workplace anticipate achieving high goals and objectives, for which an organisation is set and enshrined in its mission and vision. The article is reversed. The level of workplace equity is used to examine factors influencing workplace equity in universities, explore the impact of the workplace on employees' job satisfaction, and identify workplace equity strategies to enhance employee job satisfaction. The reviewed articles provided a standpoint view for the audience to understand the workplace, staff participation in staff academic staff, welfare and retention of employees. Herzberg's two-factor theory was significant in this review as descriptive surveys using both quantitative and qualitative methods were applied. The existing literature review identifies Herzberg's theory and practices of human resources management as having extensive knowledge for top managers in faculties, supervisors and policymakers to share and review at different levels of administration and management in Ugandan universities and beyond.

Keywords: Recruitment, promotion ranks, criteria, merit appointment, performance, quality assurance, collegiality, Welfare and mutual benefits, transformational leadership.

Cite this article:

Tugaineyo, A., (2024). Workplace Equity and Job Satisfaction among Academic Staff in Western Uganda Universities. *ISAR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(8), 59-67.

Introduction

Workplace equity in academia aims to ensure fair treatment and opportunities for career advancement among faculty members, regardless of gender, race, or background. The existing literature review reveals persistent disparities in compensation, rewards of non-financial wages, promotion rates and leadership positions, influenced by implicit biases in hiring and promotion processes (Garrick, Johnson & Arendt, 2024). Workplace equity and job satisfaction are pivotal to the success and well-being of academic staff. This article investigates the interplay between workplace equity and job satisfaction, employing Herzberg's two-factor motivational and hygiene theory. The detailed theoretical framework, empirical frameworks, empirical evidence, and practical implications elucidate their significance in higher educational institutions.

There is a growing concern about the low productivity of academic staff in terms of teaching, giving feedback on students' research papers, research and publication among academia, industrial income not being exploited, exaggerated publication of dissatisfaction of lecturers and professors do appear on platforms rather than issues of administration within university boundaries, which appear as manifestation of poor workplace equity that require a deep investigation that is anticipated to cause a paradigm shift in employees engagement (Mehrad, Halimatussadiyah,

Hamsan, Redzuan & Abdullah., 2018). The quality of higher education institutions that universities and other tertiary institutions largely depends on scholarly interaction between academic staff and learners in collaborations with other researchers and research organisations in north-south or south-to-south university collaboration. The university's collaboration is failing because university academics have nothing to put on the market hence cutting off the link between global North university researchers institutions.

Workplace equity significantly influences job satisfaction among academic staff in universities.

Objectives

1. To establish participants' knowledge about workplace equity and academic staff job satisfaction in Ugandan universities.
2. To examine factors influencing workplace equity and academic staff Job satisfaction in Ugandan universities
3. To explore the impact of workplace equity on employees' job satisfaction in Ugandan universities
4. To identify strategies to enhance workplace equity and academic staff job satisfaction in Ugandan universities

Methodology

The Documentary analysis was conducted using the Google Scholar Search Engine. The following words and concepts such as; equity, workplace equity, salary, compensations, retention, labour turnover, fairness, participation in university administration committees, welfare, and academic job satisfaction were used in the search for articles, theses, and eBooks. Desk review is a process where an individual examines the existing documents or data related to a specific topic to gather information. The primary objective of desk review is to identify relevant data sources, assess quality data, and identify gaps where further research may be needed. A review article is written to summarize the current state of understanding of a topic, and peer-reviewing articles require a slightly different set of criteria to compared with empirical articles. Unless it is a systematic review/meta-analysis methods are not important or reported (Wolbring & Nguyen, 2023). Gather research to inform your introduction and make it broad enough to reach out to a large audience of non-specialists. This will help maximize its wider relevance and impact. Don't make your introduction too long. Divide the review into sections of a suitable length to allow key points to be identified more easily (Gulpinar & Guclur, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which posits that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are influenced by separate sets of factors. Hygiene factors, such as salary, working conditions, and organizational policies (e.g., workplace equity and staff welfare), prevent dissatisfaction when adequate but do not directly contribute to satisfaction. Motivational factors, including recognition, achievement, and growth opportunities (e.g., participation in committees and career advancement), directly impact satisfaction and intrinsic motivation (Herzberg, 1968). This theory provides a comprehensive lens for understanding the complex interplay of factors affecting job satisfaction and well-being among academic staff in both public and private universities.

Herzberg's theory tends to support initiatives and management based on the equity theory which elucidates fairness at the workplace. "Equity theory predicts that employees will be happiest when their input and outcome are equal to their comparison level (Main, 2024). If a person's input is greater than, their comparison level, they will feel overworked and underappreciated". As participants (stakeholders) in education argue that, organisational justice is needed to have mutual benefits for both employees and employers, the Herzberg two-factor theory becomes relevant (Jameel, 2020). Organisational Justice (OJ) captures a wide range of workplace attitudes and highlights the importance of equality and equity as a prerequisite for organisations to function effectively. Equity is being fair and impartial in productive operations where employees and delegated managers of the employers constantly struggle to co-exist at the workplace. Several organisational policies have stood as ivory towers since many of them stand to convict subordinates rather than helping them mutually benefit from their participation. In several workplaces, sexual harassment has befallen women employees as illustrated in the "No Excuse campaign against sexual harassment" (Okille, 2019). Workplace equity is a desire for low-rank employees as employers are too busy to listen to the current outcry of workplace equity in universities.

Finally, workplace equity refers to the administrative act of ensuring fairness and impartiality in opportunities, treatment, and advancement for all employees, regardless of their race, gender, age, disabilities, religion, or any other characteristic that could be the basis for discrimination. Equity in the workplace is about ensuring all employees access the same opportunities, resources, and treatment. Equity means employees are valued based on their skills, knowledge, and abilities in a workplace, rather than their characteristics (Ilo, 2015). It involves creating a work environment where every individual has access to the same opportunities and resources, and where diversity is respected and valued. Achieving workplace equity often involves addressing system barriers, biases, and inequalities that may exist within organisations. A workplace encouraging equality, diversity and inclusion can help: make it more successful. Workplace equity keeps employees happy and motivated. It prevents serious or legal issues from arising, such as bullying, harassment and discrimination (Mushemeza, 2016; Kiiza, 2021).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria are conditions that qualify the article, thesis or book on the list of scholarly documents to be reviewed. The inclusion criteria have the above two kinds of keywords (workplace equity, welfare, job satisfaction, motivation, recognition, etc). Among the inclusion criteria a document should have a place of the study area, author (s), identified methodological approach, publication date, publisher, references, and objectives that are met or achieved. Exclusion criteria, any document that doesn't the identified inclusion criteria above will not be included in the review. To do a systematic review, systematically and transparently they develop rules about which studies can be selected for the review. Selection criteria (sometimes referred to as inclusion or exclusion criteria) create restrictions on the review. All reviews, whether systematic or not, limit in some way the studies considered by the review (Richter et al 2020).

Data Presentation and Discussion

A total of 689 books were observed, as articles, thesis and research papers written from countries such as; Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, Turkey, India, Canada, the United States of America, Australia, South Africa, the UK London, Portugal, Japan, Nigeria, and several countries. Workplace equity, employees' participation in decision-making, administrative sub-committees, employees' welfare, and job satisfaction in education institutions (schools, colleges and universities), business companies or industries, hospitals, hotels, agriculture farmers of cocoa in Uganda and social organisations like cooperative societies have been largely considered by researchers when exploring the relationship between workplace equity and job satisfaction (Wolbring & Nguyen, 2023).

The words and concepts were; workplace equity, welfare, and job satisfaction included in the search using Google Search engine. Antecedent words were; salary, employees, job satisfaction, contracts, appointments, belonging, appreciated, satisfaction, recognition, rewards, compensation, workload, opportunities, mutual benefits, regulations, and several other words such as retire, turnover, responsibilities, organisation justice, impartiality, accountability, and decolonization (Wolbring & Nguyen, 2023). The keywords helped the researcher to identify other such engines such as; PubMed, Scopus, web of Science, IEEE Explore, scienceDirect, Psycinfo, EBSCOITo, Psycho, and Proquest (Kabaka, 2014). As several software review tools are available;

EPPI-reviewer, covidence, DistellerSR, System for the Unified Management, Assessment and Review of Information (SUMARI), ayan QCRI, and SysRev, the research did not use any of the software review tools. The following hindrances were identified; lack of sufficient training in the application of the tools, lack of Firefox, and lack of competent (PC) compute handset.

The criteria to eliminate some of the articles, thesis, and books depended on the relevance of the topic and choice of instruction from the mother university; Valley University of Science and Technology which provides instruction that at least five references to be reviewed. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are explained below. The keywords of documents established from the study title and objectives were major criteria to establish which article or thesis was systematically reviewed. The area of publication like articles and thesis in Uganda were highly considered to avoid duplication of study since the author is a doctoral student of Mbarara University of Science and Technology. The study locale is western Ugandan universities hence Ugandan articles were strongly reviewed.

Workplace equity is a critical area of study because several employees in Uganda don't understand workplace rights (CPA Uganda, 2019). The challenge of not claiming their rights is shielded by a lack of written contracts as university employers sometimes offer oral contracts. contract of service "means any contract, whether oral or in writing, whether express or implied, where a person agrees in return for remuneration, to work for an employer and includes a contract of apprenticeship" (Uganda Labour Act, 2006). The authority or empowerment of employees is confidently given by the employer when he/she offers a written contract (Kibalirwandi, 2019).

Knowledge about workplace equity:

Workplace equity refers to the principle of ensuring fairness and impartiality in all aspects of employment. It involves treating all employees fairly, regardless of their background, characteristics, or personal circumstances. Fairness and equity in the workplace mean respecting the human rights of each individual who works within the organisation. Employees who feel respected by their organisation are more likely to enjoy their jobs, reach out to help their colleagues and ultimately produce better work. All of these aspects will help revitalize workplace culture and ensure your organisation is a fulfilling place to work (Liu et al, 2017).

Workplace equity aims to create a work environment where equal access to opportunities, resources, and rewards based on skills, qualifications and performance (Toker, 2011). It focuses on eliminating discrimination, biases, and barriers that may prevent individuals from reaching their full potential in the workplace. In essence, workplace equity promotes a level playing field where diversity is respected and every employee has the chance to thrive and succeed based on merit and equal treatment (Garrick, Johnson & Arendt, 2024). Equity in the workplace is about ensuring all employees access the same opportunities, resources, and treatment. Equity means employees are valued based on their skills, knowledge, and abilities in a workplace, rather than their characteristics (Wolbring & Nguyen, 2023).

Factors influencing workplace equity and Job satisfaction

Equity is distinct from equality in that it doesn't provide the same resources and opportunities to everyone (Hundrev, 2021). With equity, an organization will recognize that each employee has varying access to resources and privileges. And those with less access may need more support to take fair advantage of opportunities within a given company (Ryan et al 2020). Prioritizing wage and salary equity the payroll should have a high level of transparency. Private universities in Uganda don't have salary scale transparency. The salary scale reads different figures of salary and what goes into account reads different figures altogether (Tibarimbasa, 2010). About 85.1% of employees in Ugandan universities earn less than Ug. X 3,170,000 or US\$ 833 per month. In public universities several employees are not on the government payroll hence they are paid less than Ug. shillings 2,000,000 per month (Kibalirwandi, 2019). Diverse representation is needed to ensure workplace equity.

For instance, representation on administrative committees should be of diverse cross-level representation like gender, race, tribe, nationalities, religion, level of education, rank, etc. It is on record that marginalization is rampant in universities and other workplaces (Hundrev, 2021; Liu, 2018; Mushemeza, 2016). Invest in workforce education provides the marginalized work-life change resource to the employees hence this increases the sense of belonging. It should be important for every employer to make job descriptions accessible to all employees. Shift to skill hiring is important like a security guard or serviceman may enrol for driving and acquire skills, and a license after on-job training. organisations use inclusive non-wage as an incentive to appreciate and recognise the best outstanding employees of the month or the year.

This should be at all levels based on criteria set in handbooks and nominations at every department. Provide equitable access to all employees at all levels. Workplace equity provides access to scholarships, training opportunities, medical services, annual leave of absence, promotions, housing allowance and retirement benefits. Employees should be empowered by contracts or appointments and delegation where an employee decides on behalf of the institution and top management can defend. quality assurance policy allows staff to review curriculum and programs. Once employees have reviewed the curriculum, the vice-chancellor should be able to sign the document before submitted to NCHE. The nuances have been done by the delegated employees of the university on behalf of the vice-chancellor (Kibalirwandi, 2019). Empowerment is highly appreciated and makes employees comfortable at work hence increasing morale.

Strategies to enhance workplace equity

Several scholars have studied employment inequalities (Garrick, Johnson & Arendt, 2024). Underrepresentation and discrimination frustrate workplace equity. Nepotism and corruption where top management either fails to account for funds or engages in female workers' sexual harassment. The behaviours and actions that undermine workplace equity are barriers to development and job satisfaction.

Summary from the table below

The Doctoral Thesis of Avitus K. M. Tibarimbasa was a field research in seven private Universities; Kabale University, Kampala International University, Nkumba University, Uganda Martyrs University, Bugema University, Uganda Christian University, and Islamic University in Uganda. In his finding, 39.4% of the participants disagree that universities do not get adequate lecturers for students to get sufficient knowledge. It was further, explained that PhD holders are not adequately distributed across universities. The challenge may be low remunerations generalized as poor working conditions (Tibarimbasa, 2010). However, the topic and objectives did not include exact words such as workplace equity and job satisfaction. The definition of institutional management practices as, "an integral part of the processes of organisational development in times of change", underscores the need for workplace equity. When considering issues like diversity management, financial management, relationship management, and staffing processes, Tibarimbasa identifies a critical concept of quality assurance which is a policy aiming at improving the quality of higher education institutions (Kibaliwandu, 2019). The psychological contracts and organisational policies need to create harmony for employees to develop a sense of belonging hence job satisfaction. Financial management is part of the conditions that influence workplace equity, Tibarimbasa argues that several private universities display false audit salary scales that are never implemented by the university administration. The existing university policies favour few employees (Kibaliwandu, 2019).

Elijah Dickens Mushemeza (2016) argues that appointment, recruitment, and promotion depend highly on academic staff productivity. Keywords include; academic staff, productivity, development, core responsibilities of staff, low morale, funding challenges, inadequate staff remuneration, resignations/turnovers, limited time for research, and inability to pay for household utilities, and food. Despite the failure to have sufficient workplace equity, several universities don't display their academic staff profile pages on their university websites (Mushemeza, 2016). Mushemeza further argues that the "productivity of the academic staff should therefore be measured in terms of teaching load and the candidates graduated, research being undertaken and completed, publication of Journal articles, books, monographs and community outreach" (Mushemeza, 2016). No university Rectorate can claim that it has it all because the core activities of universities are; teaching, research and community outreach. The independent review of quality assurance shows that Ugandan universities have only complied with quality assurance policy implementation at 67.5% because most universities don't have institutional quality assurance policies approved by the university council. Some of the quality assurance offices are not functional hence the resistance to quality assurance policy implementation is at large (Kibaliwandu, 2019).

Boren Toker (2011) identifies several key works associated with workplace equity. Job satisfaction has been found to significantly influence absenteeism, turnover, job performance, and psychological distress. He further revealed that job dissatisfaction is among the best predictors of turnover. Employees' mutual

benefits affect their job satisfaction as also identified when discussing the theoretical framework where the motivational factor is well elaborated (Main, 2024; Jameel, 2020). Several antecedents of job satisfaction have been studied over Job satisfaction of academic staff including compensation, opportunity for advancement, leadership style, work environment, organizational structure and climate (Toker, 2011). The workplace environment can easily be explained through the lens of workplace equity hence, Toker's (2011) study in Turkey is significant for universities in Uganda and beyond.

Mustafa (2019) arguably presents an important topic with well-articulated keywords; workplace equity, hard work, praise, salaries, appreciation, and recognition to have loveable workplace equity for mutual benefit to employees and employers. Herzberg's two-factor motivational and hygiene theory is relevant for the analysis review of this article. The hygiene factor is about the working environment while the motivational factor is about mutual benefits (Uganda Labour Act, 2006; Herzberg, 2003).

Gregor Wolbring and Annie Nguyen, (2023) arguably state that equity is the removal of systemic barriers and biases to enact the practice of fair and equitable treatment so that all individuals have equal access to and can benefit from the programs (Wolbring & Nguyen, 2023). The study had similar keywords like workplace equity, compensation, and productivity of academic staff and several that qualify the study to be relevant to this review of the doctoral protocol as earlier mentioned. Higher education Institutions (HEIs) must proactively identify and address systemic barriers in their policies and work environments. Workplace equity is a catchword worth researching in Ugandan universities during the era of quality assurance policy implementation (Kibaliwandu, 2019).

Epiphany Odubuker Picho in his submission, identified formal recognition was not in several universities yet employees wanted to be appreciated. Of the study participants 46% disagree and 36% agree with the situation of formal recognition. It was identified that co-workers recognized employees who make a difference in productivity at work. Also, it was reported by 56% of participants that their contribution is valued at their place of work (Picho, 2014). The study ideally presents workplace equity within Ugandan academic institutions of higher learning.

George Rubasimbira (2015) study was in a western Ugandan university; Bishop Stuart. The researcher investigated motivational strategies and employees' job satisfaction by considering a few articles locally done within the same university (UMI) as Picho had just presented his study on employees' job satisfaction. Most universities don't include job satisfaction among their priority lists (Picho, 2014). He (Picho, 2014) recommends employee reward while Rubasimbira (2015) also recommends work-life balance where recreational games for staff, rewards, and recognition are pertinent for job satisfaction. The work environment, compensation, career development, and superior-subordinate relationships were some of the motivational strategies identified as important for university management.

Reviewed papers and critics based on keywords, citation papers, and journal of publication

Author (s)	Keywords	Number of References	Area of research/locale & Methods	Journal of publication	Evidence to show the aims of the study	Citations
Tibarimbasa (2010);	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Financial management -diversity mgt practices -relationship mgt -staffing processes -recruitment -Psychological contracts -organisation policies 	117	<p>Universities in West & central Uganda</p> <p>Questionnaire</p>	Doctoral Thesis on Makerere University handle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Student enrollment affects mgt of private universities -Human resource situation affects mgt of private universities -the flow of finances affect mgt of private Universities. 	41 on Makerere University handle
Mushemeza, (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Academic staff -productivity -Development -core responsibilities of staff -low morale -funding challenges -inadequate staff remuneration -resignations/turnovers -limited time for research -inability to pay for household utilities, food, school fees, and health care bills -low productivity in research and innovation 	30	<p>African universities with a focus on Makerere University in Uganda.</p> <p>Desk-Research/ review of the literature</p>	International Journal of Higher Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -identified financial challenges -failure of implementation strategies for several policies -identify challenges of recruitment in several universities. 	119 citations,
Toker, B (2011)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Job satisfaction, -workplace environment -leadership styles -opportunities for advancement placement 	27	Turkey	<p>Publisher: Sharon Parkinson</p> <p>-A questionnaire-based study was conducted in</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -to investigate the level of staff job satisfaction. 	648 citations

	-organisation strature -employee compensation			648 academicians working in the Universities of Turkey		
Mustafa (2019)	-Equity, -Equal Employment Opportunity, -Business Law, -Job Satisfaction -inputs such as tolerance, flexibility, commitment, hard work, loyalty, truth worth, determination, etc -output such as salary, thanks, recognition, job security, reputation, praise, employee benefits, etc	69	Turkey	International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management (IJEBM) Field Research where a questionnaire was applied.	-the equity theory emphasises on mutual benefits of the organisation (employer) and employees benefits. -the theory emphasises inputs and outputs to be a responsibility and benefit to both parties.	01 citation
Wolbring & Nguyen, (2023)	-Equity, -equality, -diversity, -inclusion -Workplace equity	469	Canada	https://www.mdpi.com/2813-4346/2/1/11 Review of the literature; systematics review	-The study explored the concept of “workplace” which is one area of EDI efforts cover. -identifying the workplaces mentioned	12 citations
Picho, (2014)	-job satisfaction priorities -workplace environment -recognition -appreciation -compensation -rewards		Uganda	Uganda Management Institute -Filed research was conducted and A cross-sectional survey design was used		
Rubasimbira (2015)	-Career growth -work-life balance -Job satisfaction		Uganda A study at Bishop Stuart University	UMI –Uganda Management Institute Field research		

Conclusion

Based on research objective one which states, “to establish participants' knowledge about workplace equity and academic staff job satisfaction concepts in universities, the review paper reveals a comprehensive landscape of existing literature across various global contexts including Canada, Turkey, India, Japan, Australia, Nigeria, Kenya, Uganda, and more.

The findings underscore a rich tapestry of studies focusing on job satisfaction and the working environment within academic settings, highlighting both common themes and regional variations. Authors have extensively explored factors influencing workplace equity, staff welfare, productivity, and job satisfaction, emphasizing the critical role these factors play in shaping organizational dynamics and employee well-being.

In conclusion, while the review paper consolidates existing knowledge and perspectives on workplace equity and job satisfaction in universities, it underscores the imperative for future research efforts to delve deeper into these areas through rigorous empirical investigations. This approach will facilitate the development of targeted interventions and policies aimed at fostering inclusive and supportive work environments conducive to employee satisfaction and organizational success.

The second objective is to examine factors influencing workplace equity and academic staff Job satisfaction in Ugandan universities

Firstly, the prioritization of job satisfaction by university administrators emerges as a significant issue. The review indicates that job satisfaction may not be adequately considered in administrative priorities, potentially leading to disparities in treatment and inadequate support for academic staff.

Secondly, the concept of psychological contracts—or the unwritten expectations and obligations between employees and employers—plays a crucial role. Lastly, the review underscores the financial challenges faced by academic staff, particularly in private universities where salaries are often low. This financial strain not only affects the well-being of staff members but also impacts their families' ability to meet basic needs, such as food and healthcare.

In conclusion, the review paper highlights the complex interplay of factors influencing workplace equity and job satisfaction among academic staff in Ugandan universities. It emphasizes the urgent need for university administrators to prioritize job satisfaction, address psychological contract issues, and improve financial conditions for academic staff. Addressing these challenges is essential for creating a supportive and equitable work environment that promotes employee well-being and enhances overall organizational effectiveness in the higher education sector.

The third objective states, “To explore the impact of workplace equity on employees' job satisfaction in Ugandan universities”.

Firstly, the review indicates that workplace equity issues significantly impact job satisfaction among employees in Ugandan universities. Poor working conditions, including inadequate resources, infrastructure, and support systems, contribute to dissatisfaction among academic staff.

Secondly, productivity levels in core university activities such as teaching, research, and community outreach appear to be suboptimal. This suggests that despite the critical importance of

these activities, barriers related to workplace equity may hinder their full achievement.

In conclusion, the review underscores the imperative for Ugandan universities to address workplace equity issues effectively to improve job satisfaction and productivity among academic staff. This includes investing in better working conditions, fostering a supportive organizational culture, and conducting further research to identify and mitigate barriers to productivity. By prioritizing these efforts, universities can create a conducive environment that empowers employees, enhances their job satisfaction, and ultimately elevates the quality of education and research outcomes in Uganda.

Forth objective states, “To identify strategies to enhance workplace equity and academic staff job satisfaction in Ugandan universities

Based on objective four, which aims to identify strategies to enhance workplace equity in Ugandan universities and improve academic staff job satisfaction, the review integrates insights from Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory to propose actionable recommendations. Herzberg's theory distinguishes between motivators (factors that lead to satisfaction) and hygiene factors (factors that prevent dissatisfaction). Applying this framework to the context of Ugandan universities, several strategies can be proposed:

Focus on Motivators: Enhance motivators such as recognition, achievement, and growth opportunities. Establish clear paths for career advancement, provide meaningful professional development opportunities, and celebrate academic achievements to foster job satisfaction among staff.

Address Hygiene Factors: Mitigate hygiene factors such as inadequate pay, poor working conditions, and bureaucratic constraints. Improve salary structures to be competitive within the sector, invest in infrastructure and resources for teaching and research, and streamline administrative processes to reduce frustration and enhance job satisfaction.

Promote Inclusive Leadership: Foster inclusive leadership practices that promote fairness, transparency, and participatory decision-making. Engage academic staff in decision-making processes related to curriculum development, resource allocation, and policy formulation to enhance their sense of ownership and commitment.

Support Psychological Contracts: Ensure that psychological contracts between the university and its employees are respected and fulfilled. Clarify expectations, provide support for work-life balance, and uphold commitments regarding career progression and professional support.

Continuous Feedback and Improvement: Implement mechanisms for continuous improvement on feedback from academic staff to assess workplace equity and job satisfaction. Use this feedback to inform organizational policies and practices, ensuring they are responsive to the evolving needs and expectations of employees.

In conclusion, leveraging Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory provides a structured approach to enhancing workplace equity and improving job satisfaction among academic staff in Ugandan universities.

Recommendations

The review also identifies a significant gap: there is a need for more empirical research to substantiate theoretical frameworks and anecdotal evidence. Many review papers call for field research that can provide robust empirical data to validate and expand upon the insights gathered from existing literature. Such empirical studies would not only enrich our understanding of workplace dynamics but also inform evidence-based strategies for enhancing workplace equity and improving job satisfaction among academic staff worldwide.

The review suggests that these contracts are often not fulfilled in Ugandan universities, contributing to feelings of frustration and disillusionment among academic staff.

Furthermore, the review highlights the need for further research to delve deeper into the underlying reasons for low productivity. Understanding these factors—whether they stem from organizational policies, leadership practices, resource constraints, or other systemic issues—is crucial for developing targeted interventions to enhance productivity and job satisfaction.

By addressing both motivators and hygiene factors, institutions can create a supportive and empowering environment that fosters employee engagement, enhances productivity, and ultimately contributes to the overall excellence of higher education in Uganda.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank my fellow university workers at Valley University of Science and Technology. I would also like to thank Moses Muhindo Kibalarwandi my fellow PhD student at Mbarara University of Science and Technology who became an important academic editor of my review paper. I would like to thank all scholars whose articles, theses and books I have seriously reviewed to establish my case to research my chosen topic: "Workplace equity, participation in staff committees, Welfare, and Job Satisfaction in private and public universities in Western Uganda". Finally, I would like to thank my supervisor Dr. Aloysius Rukundo for his unweaving advice during my proposal writing.

Disclaimer

This review article is meant to be published as a requirement for Valley University of Science and Technology to acquire skills in research and publication. Therefore, it is for scholarly purposes not to offend anyone whose work I have reviewed.

References

1. Adams, J. S. (1963). Towards an understanding of inequity. *The journal of abnormal and social psychology*, 67(5), 422.
2. Herzberg, F. (2003). One more time: How do you motivate employees? *Harvard Business Review*: 46(1), 53-62. Reprinted Reprint R0301F
3. Jameel, A. S. (2020). Organizational Justice and Performance among academic staff.
4. Jameel, A. S., Ahmad, A. R., & Mousa, T. S. (2020). Organizational justice and job performance of academic staff at public universities in Iraq. *Skyline Business Journal (2020)*, 16(1), 13-29.
5. Kibalarwandi, M. M., & Mwesigye, A. R. (2021). Financial strategies and quality assurance implementation in universities under the COVID-19 pandemic. *The Uganda Higher Education Review*, 9(2), 1. <https://pub.nkumbauniversity.ac.ug/xmlui/handle/123456789/1022>
6. Kibalarwandi, M. M., (2019). An evaluation of staff participation in quality assurance implementation in institutions of higher learning in Uganda. Draft Doctoral thesis. <http://medcraveonline.com/ebooks/An-evaluation-of-staff-participation-in-quality-assurance-implementation-in-institutions-of-higher-learning-in-Uganda.pdf>
7. Garrick, A., Johnson, W. D., & Arendt, S. W. (2024). Breaking Barriers: Strategies for Fostering Inclusivity in The Workplace. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*, 14(2), 128-152.
8. Macdonald, L. A. (2005). *Wellness at work: protecting and promoting employee health and wellbeing*. CIPD Publishing.
9. Main, P., (2024). Adam's Equity Theory. "Exploring the complexity of Equity theory in the Workplace: Understanding returns, equitable treatment, and employees satisfaction dynamics".
10. Mathews, S. L. (2018). *A quantitative examination of the relationship between organizational commitment, work-life balance and voluntary turnover intention of women faculty in the STEM disciplines within the united states*. Liberty University.
11. Liu, W., Zhao, S., Shi, L., Zhang, Z., Liu, X., Li, L. I., ... & Ni, X. (2018). Workplace violence, job satisfaction, burnout, perceived organisational support and their effects on turnover intention among Chinese nurses in tertiary hospitals: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*, 8(6), e019525. Doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-019525
12. Mehrad, A., Hamsan, H. H., Ma'rof Redzuan, & Abdullah, H. (2018). *The role of job satisfaction among academic staff at university*.
13. Mushemeza, E. D. (2016). Opportunities and Challenges of Academic Staff in Higher Education in Africa. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 5(3), 236-246.
14. Okille, A et al (2020). Experience of Sexual Harassment Against Women in the World of Work in Uganda. Retrieved from <https://www.akinamamawaafrika.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Sexual-Harassment-Study.pdf>
15. Zawacki-Richter, O., Kerres, M., Bedenlier, S., Bond, M., & Buntins, K. (2020). *Systematic reviews in educational research: Methodology, perspectives and application* (p. 161). Springer Nature.
16. Sanford, S. (2022). *Inclusion, Inc.: How to design intersectional equity into the workplace*. John Wiley & Sons.

- retrieved from
<https://kcls.bibliocommons.com/v2/record/S82C2358437>
17. Smith, A., Sturtevant, K., Bullough, E., & Stanworth, S. (2019). The Impact of Service Learning on Student Success. Utah Valley University.
18. Tibarimbasa, A. K. (2010). *Factors affecting the management of private universities in Uganda* (Doctoral dissertation, Makerere University). Retrieved from <http://makir.mak.ac.ug/handle/10570/2506>
19. Toker, B. (2011). Job satisfaction of academic staff: an empirical study on Turkey. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 19(2), 156-169.
20. Wolbring, G., & Nguyen, A. (2023). Equity/equality, diversity and inclusion, and other EDI phrases and EDI policy frameworks: A scoping review. *Trends in Higher Education*, 2(1), 168-237. <https://doi.org/10.3390/higheredu2010011>